

Propagation Anomaly in the Tropospheric Atmosphere

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ABSTRACT

Meteorological data has been processed to investigate RF propagation anomalies in tropospheric region from ground to 27 Km in space. There are two major dominant factors in tropospheric radio frequency wave propagation -- angular bending and time delay. The correction measures of these two tropospheric propagation problems have been proposed based on model-based or empirical measurements in terms of frequencies and climatic regions over the years to reduce propagation errors in telecommunication systems link analysis. This paper describes the performance of different climatological database and tropospheric models. A database has been developed to provide enough information for analyzing many different phenomena of nonionized atmosphere in terms of refractivity, time delay, range error, and angle of arrival. A combined modified exponential model and the stratified range/angle error model, which is developed by tropospheric research team at NRL, is utilized. The proposed tropospheric model, a modified exponential model, outperforms in the accuracy improvement of range and time delay errors in the low elevation angle below 10 degree to negative degree while surface weather data and reference height are required only to run ray-tracing algorithms for range, time delay, and angle of arrival error. This readily accessible tropospheric model can be applied to topographic survey and the improved accuracy of remote sensing (such as imagery and mapping of resource by optical sensors) of land and ocean.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of the effects of the atmosphere on microwave propagation necessitates a knowledge of height variation of refractive index in tropospheric and ionospheric regions. Since the magnitude of the refractive index is a function of such parameters as the geographic location on the Earth, weather, time of the day, and season of the year, it becomes an overwhelming task to analyze atmospheric propagation effects under parametric conditions. The NRL tropospheric research team has developed an atmospheric model, in which representations of average climatology data (ECMWF and

HIRAS) and meteorology data (MRF and FNL) are employed, for applications to system engineering or scientific researcher in the RF propagation field. The troposphere model code may be easily interfaced with other users. There are two data files for modified tropospheric model such as meteorology and reference height data. These two data files should generate more accurate time delay, range error, and angle of arrival error because these data files consist of weather data and reference coefficient height for each grid rather than an average constant[1 -3].

Data source and processed surface and reference coefficient data that was applied in this paper is presented in section 2. The modified exponential model and stratified layer method are introduced in section 3. Results of this study are explained in section 4. Finally, the conclusion and reference are in section 5.

2. DATA SOURCES AND PROCESSED DATA

Climatological data are obtained from numerous sources including the Air Force, the Navy and the NOAA. European Center for Medium Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF) data was obtained from the US Air Force Environmental Technical Applications Center (ETAC) at Scott Air Force Base, Illinois. The data consists of averaged monthly over the years (1981-1991) with 2.5 x 2.5 degree grids. High Resolution Analysis System (HIRAS) data was also obtained from the ETAC, Scott Air Force Base, Illinois. The data includes monthly and 6-hourly averaged climatology data over a seven year period (1988 - 1994) with 2.5 x 2.5 degree grids around the world. Meteorological data of both Medium Range Forecast (MRF) and Final Analysis (FNL) are obtained from the NCDC and NOAA. MRF data includes 6 hourly diurnal meteorological data over the period of 1st January 1991 to 31st December 1996, with 2.5 x 2.5 degree around the world. FNL Data is the version of the improved MRF Data consisting of 6 hourly diurnal meteorological data over the period of 1st January 1997 to present with 1.0 x 1.0 degree resolution around the world. ECMWF and HIRAS data are delivered in unformatted ASCII text. There are 14 layers of data by geopotential height and pressure level from 10 to 1000 milibars(mbars). Other data elements include

temperature, relative humidity, latitude, longitude, date and time, dew point, and air density. MRF and FNL data are delivered in unformatted binary data. MRF data is 12 layers from the surface to the height of 50 milibars. FNL data is 13 layers from the Earth's surface to the height of 20 milibars. Data elements of MRF and FNL include geopotential height, temperature, relative humidity, total cloud cover, wind vector and speed, and pressure vertical velocity. All four data source files above are converted into the troposphere global 17-variable multilayer format (grid number, Lat., Lon., pressure, Ndry, Nwet, Ntotal, standard deviation of Ntotal, Hopfield Ht, Goad dry and wet Ht, temperature, relative humidity, Height, and standard deviation of temperature, height, and humidity) that is presented in Table 1. Occasionally, a missing values appeared in the raw data for a parameter such as relative humidity. A linear interpolation fit algorithm using the two nearest temperatures and pressures was used to interpolate the relative humidity. The 17 variable multilayer data contain several occurrences of negative height at 1000 mbars pressure level. This is due to the fact that surface pressure is less than 1000 mbars at certain geographical points. In order to use the data for raytracing, the pressure is interpolated for zero height where a negative height was presented. As a final effort, the global databas was checked to ensure that multilayers (14 layers for ECM and HIRAS, 13 layers for MRF, and 12 Layers for FNL) occurred for each reported grid and no negative heights, zero temperatures, or zero relative humidities occurred above 400 mbars. The processed 17 variable multilayer data require large amounts of memory for storage. HIRAS data need about 24 Mbytes for uncompressed data that is 4 times more than ECMWF data (6 Mbytes). MRF data need about 730 Mbytes for one year uncompressed data. FNL data need about 1.2 Gbytes for one month uncompressed data. It is inappropriate to use the processed 17 variable multilayer data for real environmental applications. Therefore, the seven variable surface data and reference height coefficient data are generated from the 17 variable multilayer data to reduce storage requirement. The surface data is defined as where the height from the surface of the sea level equals zero through interpolation process. The interpolation process uses a second order polynomial fit which seems to produce the closest approximation to the 17 variable multilayer data. The surface database (ECMWF, HIRAS, and MRF) is organized in a series of 2.5 x 2.5 degree grids and 1.0 x 1.0 degree for FNL. The surface database contains grid number, latitude, longitude, pressure (Press), refractivity (N), temperature (T), and relative humidity (RH).

The reference height coefficient data consists of hourly/daily/monthly height coefficients, undulation value and time-, range-, angle of arrival error- standard deviation of the tropospheric propagation model for each grid. The reference height (H) is a scale (or reference) height appropriate to the value of refractivity at zero height surface refractivity. A scale height is simply the height at which the value of

local refractivity is e^{-1} of the surface refractivity N_s , at which the height h is equal to the scale height H . These coefficients are used to build the tropospheric refractivity up to about 20 mbars pressure level from the surface data. The undulation of geoid is a distance between the geoid and the mathematical reference ellipsoid as measured along the ellipsoidal normal. This distance is considered positive outside, or negative inside, the reference ellipsoid.

3. MODIFIED EXPONENTIAL MODEL AND STRATIFIED LAYER APPROACH

Visual inspection of the multilayer data indicates that refractivity is a decreasing exponential function of height. In fact any local refractivity $N(h)$ can be expressed as

$$N(h) = N_s \exp\left(\frac{-h}{H}\right) \quad (1)$$

where H is a scale (or reference) height and h is local height. The refractive effect of bending and time delay beyond this layer (reference height) will be very limited since temperature and humidity does not change drastically enough to affect refractive bending in those extended areas such as tropopause, stratosphere, stratopause, free space and ionosphere above 1 GHz. This coincides with the fact that the most bending and refractive phenomena occur within this region (beneath the reference height) from the surface of the Earth. This implies that the tropospheric effects on ray bending can be approximated with the reference height without loss of any significant physical principle.

The decrease or change of the water vapor pressure (e) with height is generally variable but may be approximately exponential. Note also that the delay caused by water vapor is considerably smaller than that for dry air above 3 km to 5 km from the surface, but total water vapor content along a path is variable and not predictable with high accuracy from the surface water vapor pressure or density. Therefore, water vapor is responsible for a larger error or uncertainty in the range calculation than in dry air at lower atmosphere. This kind of exponential model is widely applicable and is reliable when any reliable climatological or meteorological data to actual refractivity profiles are applied.

Millman's stratified layer method of a raytracing divides the troposphere into discrete layers of refractivity n_i . The assigned value may come from actual meteorological measurements (our multilayer data) or from modeled atmospheres. In this study, the basic assumption is that the troposphere is considered to be stratified into m height profiles and constant refractivity profile N_m . The height profiles is created by

- 0 ~ 1,000 meters: increment 100 meter each
- 1,000 ~ 10,000 meters: increment 500 meter each
- 10,000 ~ top of troposphere: increment 1,000 meter each.

Using the refractivity and the height profiles reaching up to the tropospheric height, a ray path in the troposphere can be obtained using Snell's law and Bouger's rule for spherical geometry. The main advantage of selecting the proposed modified exponential model is to be accessible to real-time data and to be able to generate 17 variable data as accurately as the measured radiosonde data.

4. RESULTS OF DATA ANALYSIS

Range and time error parameters are dependent on the time and the geographical location. The 130 areas of interest are selected as the representative geographic and climatic global conditions for the validation of model effectiveness. Figures 1 and 2 show time delay vs. elevation angle for the Modified Exponential, Hopfield and ESS models using surface data plotted against the actual ECMWF data on February and August at Eastern USA. The results show that the Modified Exponential Model is closest to the measured data, and has been consistent regardless of area-of-interest, month, or data source. Figure 3 shows data processing flow diagram from raw data to final database for tropospheric model program. The modified exponential model provides the accuracy of less than 1% of root-mean square error (rms) from the climatology or meteorology data in comparison with the accuracy of 20 % to 30 % of rms errors for the Hopfield and other models. Therefore, this model approach has been chosen in this study as the most reliable and accurate model in comparison with other models for various different conditions.

5. CONCLUSION

The 7 variable surface data are derived from the 17 variable multilayer data for the Modified Exponential Model. This database builds a multilayer atmospheric data given the surface weather data and reference height data. The constructed atmospheric data are then used with Millman's Stratified layer method to calculate range error, time delay, and angle of arrival error. Three models are examined including Hopfield and ESS models. The time delays vary seasonally from a few nanoseconds to several tens of nanoseconds as well as monthly and locally. Elevation angle errors vary dynamically throughout seasons and regional areas especially in the low elevation angles ($\leq 6^\circ$). Database are provided in ASCII-format file and can be easily reformatted for direct-access. These databases and model source codes are available through the approval process of the NRL Commanding Officer.

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Fig1. Time Delay vs Elevation Angle Eastern USA February

Fig2. Time Delay vs Elevation Angle Eastern USA August

Fig 3. Data processing Flow Diagram for Tropospheric Propagation Database